

Automated Classification of Web Pages for Identification of Suspicious Food Products – a Feasibility Study

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Summary

A vast multitude of food products is currently offered by internet trade. The two largest platforms in Germany alone have more than 250,000 products in the sale. A manual control of these websites by the food safety authorities (e. g. regarding the sale of products with unapproved ingredients, the advertisement with misleading claim or the lack of mandatory food information) appears to be difficult not only for reasons of the necessary personnel expenditure of time but also as searches with lists of suspicious product groups or keywords (e. g. novel food ingredients) reduce the search hits to already known problems. Furthermore, this would allow the dishonest vendor to remove himself from controls by avoiding those keywords, if they become known. For these reasons, a productive approach could be to employ a software system, which identifies suspicious products automatically using data analytical methods (similar to e-mail spam filtering). In the context of a feasibility study, we have evaluated different text mining and data analysis techniques such as PCA and SVM. Using a testset with 100 products, an extremely sufficient detection quota was reached (only 1 product was false-positively classified as suspicious using SVM). This approach shows great promise to improve the food control of the internet market. Due to the complexity of the processes, such investigations could be conducted by a central authority, which would need not only expertise in the software approaches but also expert knowledge in food evaluation, which is required for training of the classification algorithms.

Zusammenfassung

Der Online-Handel mit Lebensmitteln bietet mittlerweile eine unüberschaubare Vielfalt von Produkten. Auf den zwei größten Plattformen in Deutschland werden zusammen bereits mehr als 250 000 Produkte gehandelt. Eine manuelle Kontrolle der Webseiten durch die Lebensmittelüberwachung – z. B. auf das Angebot von Produkten mit unzulässigen Stoffen, der Werbung mit irreführenden Claims oder dem Fehlen von Pflichtangaben – erscheint nicht nur wegen des dafür erforderlichen personellen Zeitaufwandes schwierig, sondern beschränkt die Suchtreffer bei der Verwendung von Listen mit auffälligen Produktgruppen oder Suchbegriffen (z. B. Novel-Food Zutaten) auch auf bereits bekannte Probleme. Außerdem bietet es unredlichen Anbietern auch die Möglichkeit, sich einer Kontrolle durch Vermeidung dieser Suchworte zu entziehen, soweit die bekannt werden. Aus diesen Gründen erscheint es zielführend, ein Softwaresystem einzusetzen, das Webseiten mit auffälligen Produkten automatisiert mittels datenanalytischen Methoden identifiziert (ähnlich einem E-Mail Spam-Filter). Im Rahmen einer Machbarkeitsstudie haben wir verschiedene Textmining- und Datenanalysemethoden wie PCA und SVM evaluiert. Bei einem Testdatensatz mit 100 Produkten konnte eine außerordentlich zufriedenstellende Trefferquote erzielt werden (lediglich eine falsch-positiv als auffällig klassifizierte Probe mit der SVM-Methode). Der Ansatz wird daher als vielversprechend angesehen, um die Lebensmittelkontrolle des Internethandels zu verbessern. Auf-

grund der Komplexität der Prozesse könnten derartige Recherchen bei einer Zentralstelle für die Kontrolle des Internethandels angesiedelt sein, wobei darauf hingewiesen wird, dass neben den Softwarekenntnissen auch ein erhebliches Expertenwissen über die Produktbewertung erforderlich ist, um die Klassifizierungsverfahren zu trainieren.

Figure 2 finden Sie im Internet unter www.dlr-online.de
→ DLR Plus und Archiv DLR,
Passwort: Fischstaebchen

1 Introduction

In several previous articles, deficits in control of the internet trade with food products were pointed out, especially in the areas of misleading claims, health claims, mandatory food information and problems regarding sampling and analysis [1–7]. There appears to be consensus that immediate action is required with the aim to provide the same level of food safety for online sales as for the conventional retail trade. The BVL suggested, for example, to establish a central authority for investigation of the internet market [8,9]. The authority could use an adequate number of experts to conduct manual searches in internet search engines [8,9]. Alternatively, the use of specific software programs to scan the internet for suspicious vendors, web pages and key words was suggested [8,9]. The BVL also noted that a manual data processing would be necessary in this case, too [8,9]. We think that the quantity of the food internet trade alone makes it impossible to successfully conduct systematic searches in a manual fashion. For example, the German Amazon food section lists over 96,000 items and the food section of eBay.de lists over 193,000 items (search conducted on Apr. 13th, 2011). The second approach that would apply software programs scanning for keywords pointing to suspicious products would probably reduce the result lists for manual evaluation, but also poses the problem that the results are reduced to already known problems. The dishonest vendor could also exclude himself from controls by avoiding those keywords.

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In this article we investigate the possibility for an automated classification of web pages without manual intervention. There are effective techniques in existence that filter out spam email, and we hypothesize that it must be possible to identify suspicious web pages selling food using similar techniques. This should lead to a largely reduced number of product pages that must be scrutinized in a manual fashion and therefore reduce the personnel effort and cost necessary for internet controls. No specific previous research on the automated classification of food or product pages on the web was identified in the literature. For the classification of web pages in general, several approaches were suggested such as principal component analysis (PCA) [10], support vector machines (SVM) [11], latent semantic indexing [12], or naïve Bayes classifier [13]. A comparison of different approaches showed that SVM turned out better than other techniques such as neural networks or linear discriminant analysis [14]. A general overview about text mining was provided in the book of *Berry and Castellanos* [15].

In the context of a feasibility study, we will apply PCA and SVM, which are available in standard software packages, to classify a test set of nutritional supplements into suspicious and unsuspecting products.

2 Materials and methods

To acquire a dataset for the feasibility study, the first 100 product web pages appearing after searching for the German term “Nahrungsergänzungsmittel” (nutritional supplement) on a large German shopping portal were manually saved as HTML-files using Internet Explorer 7.0 (Microsoft). The pages were additionally printed out and manually classified by experts for nutritional supplements aiming for a qualitative binary decision as “suspicious” or “unsuspicious”. A previously published decision tree for categorization of internet products was applied to help with the manual classification [5]. For validation purposes, 20 additional product pages were similarly downloaded and classified after one month of the original search.

To acquire a data matrix usable for PCA analysis, the software Semonitor version 4.42 (*Flamingo-Soft, Vancouver, Canada*) was applied. The program analyzes HTML-text components similar to the approach of web search engines. The “weight” parameter was chosen for the following statistical calculations. The parameter assesses the “importance” of each word. The total number of

occurrences of the word, its position on the web page, the presence of specific tags (bold text, links, title text, etc.) and other parameters are taken into account to calculate this value. The “weight” values for the first 500 words of each HTML file were combined and transferred to the software Unscrambler X version 10.0.1 (*Camo Software AS, Oslo, Norway*) for PCA analysis.

The SVM analysis of the dataset was conducted using the open-source software RapidMiner version 5.1.006 (*Rapid-I GmbH, Dortmund, Germany*) by applying the “text pre-processing and classification” template, which automatically reads the collection of HTML-files, transforms them into a word matrix and finally applies SVM. All settings were left at default values. Additionally, the word matrix of RapidMiner was transferred to Unscrambler to conduct a PCA analysis using the word matrix instead of the weight distribution. This approach allowed determining the words that are responsible for the classification.

3 Results and discussion

The first and probably largest problem for the automatic classification of web pages is to produce a dataset that can be evaluated using the available software packages. For example, the standard software for multivariate data analysis (Unscrambler) demands a simple data matrix containing numerical variables for each object (i.e. web page in our case). It is not possible to directly import HTML pages into Unscrambler. For this reason, we have preprocessed the HTML data using the Semonitor software. The resulting weight distribution is a column of numerical data for each object that can be imported into Unscrambler. The weight distribution can be interpreted as a fingerprint of the web page. The disadvantage of this approach is that the connection with the original variables gets lost during the preprocessing, so that

Fig. 1 Result of the principal component analysis (PCA). Suspicious product pages are marked as “bad” and unsuspecting products as “OK”. The suspicious products cluster in the area with negative PC1 values.

it is unknown which words ultimately led to the differences. Nevertheless, this simple approach was successful, as a clustering of suspicious products occurs (Fig. 1). However, several unsuspecting products were also contained in the cluster with suspicious products. From the 100 products in the test set, 40 % could be directly classified as unsuspecting. The other half would require manual evaluation. The validation with the independent test-set of 20 product pages showed similar performance. From the 20 pages, 5 were falling into the unsuspecting category, which was confirmed by the manual evaluation in every case. From the 15 pages that fell into the suspicious category, 7 were manually confirmed to be suspicious. This means that 60 % of the validation set were correctly classified and that no false-negative classification occurred (i. e. no manually classified suspicious product would automatically be classified as unsuspecting, which would be a worst case from a consumer's perspective).

The SVM result is shown in Figure 2. The method worked considerably better than PCA, as only one page was misclassified in this case. This basically confirmed the previous research mentioned in the introduction that SVM works better for web page classification than other methods. Similar to our PCA approach, the SVM method also does not provide the actual key words responsible for the classification.

For this reason, we have conducted a second PCA on the word matrix available from the RapidMiner software. The PCA classification using this input was inferior to the classification using the weight distribution, but the most important key words leading to classification can now be identified (over 10,000 variables were contained in this data set). These keywords included "einwandfrei" (acceptable), "behörde" (authority), "energielieferant" (energy source), "immunsystem" (immune system), "krank" (diseased), or "schokolade" (chocolate). This proves that the algorithms are able to effectively identify problematic keywords (e.g., health claim related words such as diseased or immune system) without any a priori knowledge. The use of "chocolate" as ingredient is probably an indicator that the product is unsuspecting, hence the inclusion of this term in the words is mainly responsible for classification.

In conclusion, we think that the feasibility of the approach was shown to be successful and worthwhile to be followed in the future. Optimally, a software package should combine all steps including web crawling (i. e. the downloading of HTML product pages from the internet), the data pre-treatment (i. e. consistently transferring the HTML

data into a usable dataset for classification), and finally the classification itself. Similar to spam-filters, the software should offer the constant improvement of the models when false-positive or false-negative samples are manually reclassified.

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Fig. 2 Result of the support vector machine (SVM) classification analysis. Suspicious products have a value above 0.8, and this group includes only one false-positively assigned unsuspecting product.